

EVALUATION OF THE PLASTICIZING EFFECT OF POLYETHYLENE GLYCOL 400 IN A POLYLACTIC ACID POLYMER MATRIX FOR FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATIONS

Daniel Alvarez Gomez¹, Juan Porras¹, Andrea Sánchez Camargo¹ and Alicia Porras¹

¹Products and Processes Design Group (GDPP), Department of Chemical and Food Engineering, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia

Keywords: Food packaging, Thin films, Thermal properties, Physical properties

ABSTRACT

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) is the most widely produced biopolymer worldwide, offering a biodegradable alternative to conventional plastics in food packaging applications. Its renewable origin and mechanical properties comparable to petroleum-based polymers make it a suitable candidate for environmentally responsible packaging solutions. However, PLA's inherent brittleness and low barrier performance against gases such as oxygen limit its applicability in more demanding contexts. To address these challenges, plasticizers have been incorporated into PLA matrices to enhance flexibility and improve overall material functionality. Among them, polyethylene glycol with a molecular weight of 400 Da (PEG 400) has shown promise due to its compatibility, low toxicity, and biodegradable nature.

This study investigates the effect of PEG 400 at different concentrations (0%, 20%, and 40% w/w) on the thermal, barrier, and rheological properties of PLA films prepared by solvent casting. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) coupled with mass spectrometry (MS) was used to assess thermal degradation profiles, while differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) provided information on glass transition temperature (T_g), melting temperature (T_m), and crystallinity. Oxygen transmission rate (OTR) was measured according to ASTM D3985, and oscillatory rheological tests were conducted to determine storage and loss moduli, as well as complex viscosity.

TGA results indicated that increasing PEG content decreased the onset degradation temperature from 291.12°C (0% PEG) to 203.89°C (20%) and 205.54°C (40%). Unlike the control film, which displayed an initial mass loss attributed to residual solvent evaporation, PEG-plasticized samples exhibited single-stage degradation. T_g was observed at 59°C for the control but was no longer detectable in the presence of PEG. T_m also declined from 151.73°C to 147.49°C and 140.17°C as PEG concentration increased, while crystallinity rose from 1.09% to 19.4% at 20% PEG. Barrier testing showed that OTR decreased by 50% and 25% with 20% and 40% PEG, respectively, compared to the control.

Overall, the inclusion of PEG 400 significantly altered the thermal stability, crystallinity, and oxygen barrier properties of PLA films, demonstrating its potential as an effective plasticizer for bio-based food packaging materials

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most notable developments in sustainable food packaging materials has been the emergence of biopolymers as viable alternatives to conventional petroleum-based plastics [1]. Among these, poly(lactic acid) (PLA) stands out due to its renewable origin, biodegradability, and mechanical properties comparable to those of traditional polymers [2]. Produced through the fermentation of agricultural feedstocks such as corn or sugarcane, PLA is particularly well-suited for applications that require food safety and environmental compatibility [3]. However, its intrinsic brittleness and limited barrier performance against oxygen and moisture remain major challenges, especially in packaging for high-moisture, perishable foods [4]. To overcome these limitations, recent research has focused on modifying PLA through the incorporation of plasticizers to improve its flexibility and functional behavior [4].

Plasticizers are low molecular weight compounds added to polymers to enhance chain mobility, reduce brittleness, and improve processability [5]. Bio-based plasticizers have attracted increasing interest due to their biodegradability, low toxicity, and alignment with green chemistry principles. Polyethylene glycol (PEG) 400, in particular, has been widely studied for its compatibility with PLA and its proven safety in biomedical and food-related applications. As a hydrophilic polyether, PEG 400 effectively improves PLA ductility and elongation at break by promoting molecular mobility within the polymer matrix [6]. While its mechanical plasticizing effects are well-documented, less is known about its broader influence on the thermal, structural, and barrier properties of PLA films, especially in the context of functional or smart packaging systems [7], [8].

In this study, PLA films were prepared using PEG 400 as a plasticizer at concentrations of 0%, 20%, and 40% w/w. The impact of plasticizer content on film properties was evaluated using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) with mass spectrometry, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), oxygen transmission rate (OTR) measurements, and oscillatory rheological tests. These methods were used to investigate changes in thermal stability, transition temperatures, gas barrier performance, and viscoelastic behavior associated with increasing PEG content.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Polylactic acid (PLA, grade LX175) was supplied by TotalEnergies Corbion (Netherlands). Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400) was purchased from Merck & Co. (USA). Chloroform (analytical grade) was used as a solvent for film preparation.

2.2 Film Preparation

PLA films were prepared via solvent casting. PLA was dissolved in chloroform under magnetic stirring at room temperature. PEG 400 was added at 0%, 20%, and 40% w/w relative to PLA mass. The mixture was stirred until complete homogenization and cast into Petri dishes. Films were dried under controlled conditions to ensure solvent evaporation. Formulations containing anthocyanins were prepared by incorporating the lyophilized extract into the PLA-PEG matrix prior to casting.

2.3 Thermal Analysis

Thermal degradation behavior was evaluated through thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a heating rate of 10°C/min under a nitrogen atmosphere. The onset degradation temperature and weight loss profiles were recorded. Additionally, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to determine the glass transition temperature (T_g), melting temperature (T_m), and crystallinity of the films. Samples were heated from 30°C to 200°C at a rate of 10°C/min under nitrogen flow.

2.4 Oxygen Permeability

The oxygen transmission rate (OTR) of the films was measured according to the ASTM D3985 standard using a coulometric sensor. The tests were performed at 0% relative humidity and 23°C. Results were reported in $\text{cm}^3/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{day}$.

2.5 Rheological Properties

The rheological behavior of the PLA-PEG formulations was assessed by oscillatory frequency sweep tests. Measurements were carried out using a parallel plate rheometer at the melting temperature of each formulation. Storage modulus (G'), loss modulus (G''), and complex viscosity (η^*) were recorded over a frequency range of 0.1–100 Hz.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal Analysis

Figure 1.a. TGA curves of PLA-PEG blends. **b.** DTGA curves of PLA-PEG blends

Figure 1. exhibits the TGA results for the films formulations. The control film (PLA100) exhibited two degradation stages: an initial 8.4% weight loss between 72°C and 166°C due to residual chloroform, and a major degradation between 291°C and 374°C, peaking at 356°C, attributed to PLA chain scission.

In contrast, films with PEG400 (PEG20 and PEG40) showed a single degradation stage starting at lower temperatures (203°C and 205°C, respectively), due to PEG decomposition and its plasticizing effect, which reduces intermolecular interactions and promotes chain mobility. The maximum degradation temperatures decreased to 299°C (PEG20) and 284°C (PEG40), indicating reduced thermal resistance.

Derivative TGA curves revealed broader and less symmetric peaks for PEG-containing films, suggesting a more complex, phase-separated degradation behavior. The absence of early weight loss in these films implies that PEG facilitates solvent removal during drying, likely by altering PLA packing and enhancing solvent volatility.

Figure 2. DSC curves for the PLA-PEG blends **a.)** second heating and **b.)** cooling of the formulations.

Overall, PEG400 improves polymer chain mobility and solvent release, but reduces thermal stability, an acceptable compromise for applications such as refrigerated or ambient food packaging.

3.2 Barrier Properties

Figure 2. displays the DSC results for the films formulations. The control sample (PLA100) exhibited three characteristic transitions: glass transition temperature at 59.62°C, cold crystallization at 122.66°C, and melting at 151.73°C. These behaviors are typical of semicrystalline PLA.

With PEG addition, thermal properties changed notably. The melting temperature decreased to 147.49°C (PEG20) and 140.17°C (PEG40), indicating weaker intermolecular forces due to PEG insertion between PLA chains. The cold crystallization temperature dropped significantly to 73.76°C (PEG20) and disappeared in PEG40 during heating, though it was observed during cooling, suggesting phase separation and altered nucleation behavior.

Film crystallinity increased with PEG content, from 1.09% in PLA100 to 13.90% (PEG20) and 29.18% (PEG40). PEG likely acts as a heterogeneous nucleating agent, facilitating PLA chain organization. Additionally, the glass transition became undetectable in plasticized samples, attributed to increased free volume and enhanced chain mobility induced by PEG.

Overall, PEG400 significantly influences PLA's thermal behavior by lowering T_g and T_m , promoting crystallinity, and modifying crystallization dynamics—effects that are beneficial for tailoring the performance of biodegradable films in food packaging applications.

Figure 3. OTR of the biofilms.

Oxygen barrier performance in PLA–PEG blends is governed by crystalline structure, polymer mobility, and phase morphology. Figure 3 shows the OTR of the films. In pure PLA (PLA100), the OTR was 161.68 ± 4.1 cm³/m²·day, reflecting its moderate crystallinity and loose molecular packing. Incorporation of 20% PEG400 (PEG20) reduced OTR to 84.78 ± 3.7 cm³/m²·day, attributed to increased crystallinity and improved molecular packing that hinder gas diffusion.

However, further increasing PEG to 40% (PEG40) raised OTR to 125.36 ± 3.9 cm³/m²·day. This reduction in barrier performance is linked to PEG-induced phase separation. At high concentrations, PEG becomes partially immiscible, forming amorphous microdomains that act as permeable pathways for oxygen. These domains interrupt the crystalline PLA matrix, reduce ordering, and enhance chain mobility, factors that facilitate gas transport.

Overall, optimal oxygen barrier performance is achieved at intermediate PEG levels (~20%), highlighting the critical balance between crystallization and plasticization in the design of biodegradable packaging films.

3.3 Rheological Properties

Figure 4. Frequency dependent storage and loss modulus of the PLA-PEG blends a.) PLA100, b.) PEG20, c.) PEG40.

The rheological analysis of PLA-PEG blends revealed significant changes in viscoelastic behavior with increasing PEG content. Figure 4 exhibits the results of the frequency sweep test. For neat PLA (PLA100), the storage modulus (G') exceeded the loss modulus (G''), indicating a predominantly elastic response. However, with PEG addition (PEG20 and PEG40), G'' remained higher across all frequencies, suggesting a transition toward viscoelastic fluid behavior and loss of structural rigidity.

A pronounced decrease in G' (over three orders of magnitude) and a slight increase in G'' were observed, reflecting reduced stiffness and enhanced chain mobility due to the plasticizing effect of PEG. This softening is attributed to PEG's disruption of PLA's intermolecular interactions, such as van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonding.

Figure 5. Complex viscosity (η^*) of the PLA-PEG blends.

Complex viscosity (Figure 5) decreased markedly with PEG content, particularly at low frequencies, indicating lower chain entanglement and greater flowability. Additionally, PLA100 showed strong shear-thinning behavior, while PEG-containing blends approached more Newtonian flow due to reduced elastic constraints. Overall, PEG400 significantly lowers the elastic character and viscosity of PLA, enhancing flexibility and processability, key attributes for applications like biodegradable film packaging.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that incorporating PEG400 into PLA matrices significantly alters the thermal, barrier, and rheological properties of the resulting films. Thermogravimetric analysis showed that PEG reduced thermal stability by lowering the onset and maximum degradation temperatures, while also facilitating solvent removal during processing. Differential scanning calorimetry revealed that PEG enhances crystallinity and chain mobility, as evidenced by reduced glass transition and melting temperatures, and the disappearance of cold crystallization at higher PEG levels. Oxygen transmission rate measurements indicated that a moderate PEG content (20% w/w) optimized barrier performance by promoting crystallinity, whereas higher concentrations (40% w/w) induced phase separation, diminishing oxygen resistance. Rheological tests confirmed that PEG acts as an effective plasticizer, decreasing stiffness and complex viscosity, and shifting material behavior from elastic to viscoelastic. Collectively, these findings highlight PEG400's dual role as a plasticizer and structural modifier, with 20% w/w emerging as the optimal concentration for enhancing film performance in sustainable food packaging applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express their gratitude to the Department of Chemical and Food Engineering at Universidad de los Andes and to the Products and Processes Design Group (GDPP) for their valuable technical and academic support throughout the development of this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. A. Swetha *et al.*, "A comprehensive review on polylactic acid (PLA) – Synthesis, processing and application in food packaging," Apr. 15, 2023, *Elsevier B.V.* doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2023.123715.
- [2] A. Fiore, S. Park, S. Volpe, E. Torrieri, and P. Masi, "Active packaging based on PLA and chitosan-caseinate enriched rosemary essential oil coating for fresh minced chicken breast application," *Food Packag Shelf Life*, vol. 29, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.fpsl.2021.100708.

- [3] A. Visco *et al.*, “Agri-Food Wastes for Bioplastics: European Prospective on Possible Applications in Their Second Life for a Circular Economy,” Jul. 01, 2022, *MDPI*. doi: 10.3390/polym14132752.
- [4] J. Jacob, U. Lawal, S. Thomas, and R. B. Valapa, “Biobased polymer composite from poly(lactic acid): Processing, fabrication, and characterization for food packaging,” in *Processing and Development of Polysaccharide-Based Biopolymers for Packaging Applications*, Elsevier, 2020, pp. 97–115. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-818795-1.00004-6.
- [5] M. Lu *et al.*, “A multifunctional lactic acid based plasticizer used for plasticizing PVC and PLA: Endowing PLA elastic restore capability,” *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, vol. 128, pp. 245–257, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jiec.2023.07.054.
- [6] M. M. Mazidi, S. Arezoumand, and L. Zare, “Research progress in fully biorenewable tough blends of polylactide and green plasticizers,” Nov. 01, 2024, *Elsevier B.V.* doi: 10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.135345.
- [7] A. Greco, F. Ferrari, and A. Maffezzoli, “Mechanical properties of poly(lactid acid) plasticized by cardanol derivatives,” *Polym Degrad Stab*, vol. 159, pp. 199–204, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2018.11.028.
- [8] A. Greco, F. Ferrari, and A. Maffezzoli, “Processing of super tough plasticized pla by rotational molding,” *Advances in Polymer Technology*, vol. 2019, 2019, doi: 10.1155/2019/3835829.